

WAYS TO IMPROVE AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTIVITY IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This thesis analyzes the main directions and methods of increasing the efficiency of agricultural production in Uzbekistan. The issues of increasing agricultural production, rational use of land and water resources, introduction of modern agricultural technologies and use of innovative approaches are highlighted.

Keywords: agriculture, efficient agricultural production, increasing agricultural production, land resources, water resources, rational use of resources, modern agricultural technologies, innovative approach.

O‘ZBEKISTON QISHLOQ XO‘JALIGIDA MAHSULOT YETISHTIRISH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING USULLARI

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur tezisda O‘zbekiston qishloq xo‘jaligida mahsulot yetishtirish samaradorligini oshirishning asosiy yo‘nalishlari va usullari tahlil qilinadi. Qishloq xo‘jaligida ishlab chiqarish hajmini ko‘paytirish, yer va suv resurslaridan oqilona foydalanish, zamonaviy agrotexnologiyalarni joriy etish hamda innovatsion yondashuvlardan foydalanish masalalari yoritib beriladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: qishloq xo‘jaligi, mahsulot yetishtirish samaradorli, qishloq xo‘jaligida ishlab chiqarish hajmini ko‘paytirish, yer resurslari, suv resurslari, resurslardan

oqilona foydalanish, zamonaviy agrotexnologiyalar, innovatsion yondashuv.

INTRODUCTION

The growth of the population and the growing demand for food products make increasing the efficiency of agricultural production a pressing issue. Therefore, the application of modern agrotechnologies, the efficient use of land and water resources, and the modernization of production processes are of great importance in this field. This thesis considers the main methods of increasing the efficiency of agricultural production and their practical significance.

MAIN PART

In order to more effectively use irrigated arable land, increase soil fertility and crop yields, it is important to implement scientifically based crop rotation systems, introduce and develop new areas of agriculture (Organic, Global G.A.P., etc.) in accordance with international experience, and increase soil fertility by preventing and sharply reducing agricultural land degradation.

Among the important tasks facing us are: determining the procedure for the effective use of pastures, developing and implementing scientifically based effective technologies for the use of pastures and fallow lands, determining the procedure for calculating and compensating for the costs incurred on the land allocated to a farm or other agricultural production entity when it is liquidated or optimized, determining the procedure for allocating land for gardens, vineyards, fish ponds and greenhouses, and supporting the construction of greenhouses using hydroponics and vertical farms on disused lands.

In areas with water scarcity and difficulty in cultivating and using agricultural crops, special attention should be paid to minimizing the number of agrotechnical measures by building ready-made modern greenhouses with the involvement of foreign

investors and foreign financial institutions, introducing soil-efficient technologies in agriculture, and consistently implementing advanced innovative technologies for tillage and crop care (Mini till, No till, etc.).

It is very important to develop a procedure for compensating agricultural producers for the costs associated with the introduction of technologies for improving the land reclamation, fertility, and water supply of irrigated lands, to establish mechanisms for state support for ensuring increased land fertility and productivity, and to introduce differentiated tax incentives, including mechanisms to encourage landowners to maintain and increase soil fertility (see diagram).

Diagram

Agricultural products produced in Uzbekistan in 2010-2025, billion sum

It is important to strengthen liability measures for the inefficient use of agricultural land, to legally regulate the prevention of inefficient use of land and water resources, to increase land fertility and implement water-saving agrotechnical measures (agrotechnical regulations), and to establish a procedure for declaring economically inefficient, low-yielding orchards and vineyards unsuitable and transferring them to the category of arable land.

It is necessary to develop agrochemical maps based on agrochemical analyses of soil in agricultural fields every 5 years at the expense of the state budget, collect food, farm, livestock and other organic waste from cities and suburbs, and establish the production of organic fertilizers using modern technologies and supply them to agricultural producers, establish a public-private partnership mechanism for the use of forest fund lands, and create "agricultural investment hubs" based on the agricultural potential of each region to present them to local and foreign companies.

It is necessary to make amendments and additions to the legislation that provides for the transfer of all arable land in districts with more than 50 percent of unprofitable cotton and grain areas to clusters organizing the full processing of cotton and grain, subject to the construction and reconstruction of irrigation and land reclamation networks, the allocation of the necessary funds from the state budget for the State Committee for Geology and Mineral Resources to carry out work to identify groundwater reserves suitable for irrigation of agricultural crops, and the leasing of uncultivated forest lands to citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan for use in the creation of new forests and medicinal plant plantations by forestry authorities on the terms of a public-private partnership for a period of up to 50 years.

It is of great importance to expand the use of bio-reclamation measures to protect against soil erosion and degradation, wind and hail, establish and restore protected areas, and create plantations of desert-food plants and pastures on forest lands that protect them from external environmental factors, and form a targeted list of land areas to be restored and put into use.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, increasing the efficiency of agricultural production in Uzbekistan is important for ensuring the country's food security and accelerating economic development. The introduction of modern agricultural technologies, rational use of land

and water resources, effective use of scientific achievements, and support for the activities of farms are important factors in achieving this. The consistent implementation of these measures will help increase the volume of agricultural production and further improve the efficiency of the sector.

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